

High-precision isotopic analysis sheds new light on mercury metabolism in long-finned pilot whales (*Globicephala melas*)

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Supplementary information

ABSTRACT

Whales accumulate mercury (Hg), but do not seem to show immediate evidence of toxic effects. Analysis of different tissues (liver, kidney, muscle) and biofluids (blood, milk) from a pod of stranded long-finned pilot whales (*Globicephala melas*) showed accumulation of Hg as a function of age, with a significant decrease in the MeHg fraction. Isotopic analysis revealed remarkable differences between juvenile and adult whales. During the first period of life, Hg in the liver became isotopically lighter ($\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ decreased) with a strongly decreasing methylmercury (MeHg) fraction. We suggest this is due to preferential demethylation of MeHg with the lighter Hg isotopes and transport of MeHg to less sensitive organs, such as the muscles. Also changes in diet, with high MeHg intake *in utero* and during lactation, followed by increasing consumption of solid food contribute to this behavior. Interestingly, this trend in $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ is reversed for livers of adult whales (increasing $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ value), accompanied by a progressive decrease of $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ in muscle at older ages. These total Hg (THg) isotopic trends suggest changes in the Hg metabolism of the long-finned pilot whales, development of (a) detoxification mechanism(s) (*e.g.*, though the formation of HgSe particles), and Hg redistribution across the different organs.

27 Mercury (Hg) is a toxic heavy metal that is globally distributed through the atmosphere, in which Hg
28 has a residence time of up to 1 year.^{1,2} Atmospheric Hg is predominantly deposited in oceans, one of
29 the major reservoirs of Hg on Earth.³ In aquatic environments, inorganic Hg species are converted into
30 the more toxic compound methylmercury (MeHg). This conversion proceeds *via* biotic or abiotic
31 methylation, occurring in sediments and/or in the water column.⁴ MeHg exposure of aquatic biota
32 occurs mainly *via* the diet, resulting in the bioaccumulation and biomagnification of MeHg across food
33 webs, leading to high Hg levels in predatory animals.⁵

34 Located at the top of aquatic food chains and with a long lifespan, marine mammals accumulate high
35 amounts of Hg in their tissues.^{6,7} This is an issue of great concern in terms of seafood safety, as despite
36 of the health risks, these marine species are consumed by humans at some locations around the
37 world.⁸ However, the study of marine mammals is even more relevant owing to the similarities these
38 species may share with humans in terms of metabolic pathways. It has been shown that despite the
39 high Hg concentrations present in their tissues, marine mammals do not show the toxic effects
40 observed for humans, suggesting the existence of (an) effective Hg detoxification mechanism(s).⁹ Thus,
41 study of the Hg metabolic pathways (*i.e.*, uptake, distribution and excretion) in marine mammals may
42 aid (*i*) our understanding of the behavior of Hg in humans and thus, (*ii*) the development of new
43 strategies for avoiding and/or minimizing the toxic effects induced by Hg and its compounds, such as
44 neurological damage and cardiovascular problems.

45 Some authors previously reported a species-specific Hg distribution among the different organs of
46 marine mammals,^{10,11} and pointed out the affinity of Hg for biomolecules containing S and Se. The
47 covalent binding of Hg to thiol/sulfhydryl groups is a well-known biochemical mechanism, involved in
48 transport of Hg across membranes, its redistribution across different tissue types and its
49 excretion.^{1,12,13} However, there is increasing evidence that the physiological target of Hg is not S, but
50 Se (binding of Hg to selenoproteins and selenoenzymes).^{14,15} In fact, the binding affinity between Hg
51 and Se is several orders of magnitude higher than that between Hg and S. Thus, Se may play a more
52 important role than S in Hg detoxification, especially *via* the formation of insoluble, stable and inert

53 Hg-Se bonds, *e.g.*, in HgSe particles.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ However, it needs to be noted that several studies also
54 suggested the incorporation of S into the HgSe structures.²⁰⁻²² In any case, important knowledge gaps
55 still remain in our understanding of the metabolic pathways of Hg in marine mammals.

56 The measurement of Hg isotope ratios is considered a promising approach to shed light onto the
57 biogeochemical Hg cycle in nature.^{23,24} Hg is one of the few elements that display not only mass-
58 dependent isotope fractionation (MDF; typically expressed *via* the $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ value), but also mass-
59 independent isotope fractionation (MIF; expressed using the $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ and $\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ values), thus enabling
60 a multi-dimensional approach.^{25,26} The occurrence of MDF has been documented for most of the
61 transformations that Hg undergoes in the environment, including methylation, demethylation, ligand
62 exchange, adsorption, volatilization, liquid-vapor evaporation, abiotic oxidation and reduction.²⁷⁻³⁵
63 Additionally, MIF of a large magnitude has been observed during photochemical reactions involving
64 radicals (see Methods for the definition of $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$, $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ and $\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$).³⁶ Several laboratory experiments
65 and field studies have indicated that trophic transfer of Hg and most of the *in vivo* processes it is
66 involved in are accompanied by *in vivo* MDF.^{11,37} However, *in vivo* MIF is not observed for these
67 processes, suggesting that the MIF signature of Hg – $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$, $\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ and $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}/\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ – in aquatic
68 animals (especially those located at the top of a trophic chain) is typically more useful for provenance
69 determination of the accumulated Hg than the MDF signature.^{36,38-41}

70 In this work, different tissues and biofluids (liver, kidney, muscle, blood and milk) of long-finned pilot
71 whales (*Globicephala melas*) were analyzed for their bulk or total Hg (THg) concentration, MeHg
72 concentration and THg isotope ratios. Our aim was to (i) obtain a more profound insight into the
73 metabolic processes that Hg undergoes in these marine mammals and to (ii) find evidence for effective
74 detoxification mechanisms avoiding Hg poisoning.

75

76 **Sample collection and sample types**

77 On the 12th of September 2012, 31 long-finned pilot whales (*Globicephala melas*) stranded on a beach
78 between Ansturther and Pittenween in Scotland, United Kingdom. From the complete pod, 10 whales
79 were refloated, but 21 whales died at the stranding site, where the autopsy of each animal was carried
80 out and their organs were dissected and stored for research purposes, as part of the government
81 stranding scheme, aiming to establish the reason behind Cetaceous strandings on the Scottish coast.⁹
82 We have analyzed 73 samples, comprising 21 liver samples, 20 kidney samples, 15 muscle samples, 14
83 blood samples and 1 milk sample. In addition, HgSe particles were isolated from 5 liver samples and 2
84 muscle samples, and subsequently characterized in terms of Hg isotopic composition. The age of the
85 whales was determined by Gajdosechova *et al.*⁹ following the method described by Lockyer.⁴²
86 Supplementary Table 1 provides further information (age, gender and length) on the animals analyzed
87 in this work.

88

89 **Mercury distribution in long-finned pilot whales**

90 For every individual analyzed, the highest level of Hg was found in liver (0.98 – 608 mg Kg⁻¹ wet weight,
91 w.w.), followed by kidney (0.42 – 21.8 mg Kg⁻¹ w.w.) and muscle (0.50 – 4.72 mg Kg⁻¹ w.w.) (see
92 Supplementary Tables 2, 3 and 4 for THg concentrations and MeHg fractions). This THg concentration
93 trend is in good agreement with data previously reported for marine mammals.^{6,9} Speciation analysis
94 indicated that Hg is predominantly present as MeHg in muscle (65.3 –100 %), while the MeHg fraction
95 in liver (1.0 – 32.1 %) and kidney (4.7 – 46.5 %) tends to be relatively low. Based on the assumption
96 that the Hg is mainly taken in by marine mammals from the diet (including transport across the
97 placenta before birth and *via* milk though lactating),⁴³ the relatively low MeHg fraction observed in
98 liver and kidney suggests that the MeHg ingested is slowly demethylated *in vivo* and converted into
99 inorganic Hg (iHg) forms. This iHg is stored in the liver, and to a lesser extent in the kidney (also a small
100 fraction of the iHg might be excreted from the organism), while the remaining MeHg is mainly
101 accumulated in the muscle, which acts as a reservoir for this highly toxic Hg species.^{11,41} For all tissues

102 studied, the THg concentration increases as a function of age, while the MeHg fraction decreases
103 (Figure 1). This suggests that the Hg metabolism changes over the lifespan of the whales, most likely
104 inducing a higher extent of MeHg demethylation and/or a greater accumulation of iHg, *e.g.*, under the
105 form of less toxic HgSe particles.^{10,11}

106 Also isotopic analysis of THg (Supplementary Figure 1 shows the three-isotope plots) revealed
107 important differences between the different tissues studied (see Supplementary Tables 2, 3 and 4 for
108 $\delta^{199}\text{Hg}$, $\delta^{200}\text{Hg}$, $\delta^{201}\text{Hg}$, $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$, $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ and $\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ values for liver, kidney and muscle, respectively). Low
109 $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values (a lighter isotopic composition) are found for liver (-1.23 – -0.15 ‰) and kidney (-1.10 –
110 -0.29 ‰) tissues, and higher ones for muscle (0.20 – 1.31 ‰). These differences can be broadly
111 attributed to the compound-specificity of the Hg isotopic signatures, *i.e.*, the different Hg isotopic
112 compositions of MeHg and iHg (Supplementary Figure 2 shows the $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ value as a function of MeHg
113 fraction in muscle and liver) – see next section for further details on specific trends. This could
114 theoretically stem from either different MeHg and iHg sources with different Hg isotopic signatures
115 and/or from metabolic processes occurring in the whale body, such as MeHg demethylation, and the
116 isotope fractionation accompanying these processes. However, the constant $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ and $\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ values
117 obtained for the different tissues (average values of 1.05 ± 0.05 and 0.87 ± 0.05 ‰, respectively)
118 suggest strongly that (i) there is no *in vivo* MIF accompanying the different Hg metabolic processes,
119 and that (ii) both Hg compounds have the same origin, *i.e.*, MeHg ingested *via* the diet (see
120 Supplementary Figures 3 and 4). The absence of *in vivo* MIF observed in this work is consistent with
121 previous studies.^{11,36,39,44,45} As indicated above, MeHg and the demethylation product iHg are
122 subsequently distributed differently over the organs. iHg is mainly accumulated in the liver and the
123 kidneys, whereas MeHg is preferentially excreted from the liver and subsequently accumulated in
124 muscle tissue.^{6,11,41} Therefore, differences in Hg speciation and the corresponding variations in the
125 isotopic composition of Hg in the different tissues most likely result from *in vivo* demethylation of
126 MeHg,⁴⁶ and the MDF of Hg accompanying this process (the lighter Hg isotopes are preferentially

127 demethylated), resulting in higher $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values in the remaining MeHg fraction (muscle) and in lower
128 $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values in the iHg produced (liver, kidney).⁴⁷

129

130 **Differences in mercury metabolism between juvenile and adult whales**

131 The combination of MeHg intake and *in vivo* demethylation processes in the whale body explains both
132 the Hg speciation and the bulk Hg isotopic signatures observed in general terms, but additional
133 information is obtained when looking at the results obtained into greater detail. Figure 2 shows the
134 $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values as a function of age for all tissues (muscle, liver and kidney) and biofluids (blood and
135 milk) from female and male individuals (no gender-based differences were observed within the entire
136 study).

137 *Muscle tissue*

138 We found that muscle is characterized by a high MeHg fraction, and, as a consequence, by a heavier
139 Hg isotopic composition than kidney and liver (a significant positive correlation was found between
140 muscle $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values and MeHg fractions, Spearman's correlation, $r = 0.596$, $p = 0.025$). Recent studies
141 have also reported an enrichment of approximately 1 ‰ in $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ for muscle tissue of seals relative to
142 the Hg isotopic signature of their diet.¹¹ As can be seen in Figure 3A, no significant correlations were
143 found between muscle $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values or MeHg fractions and the age of the youngest (≤ 6 years old)
144 individuals (Spearman's correlation, $r = -0.153$, $p = 0.694$ and $r = 0.000$, $p = 1.00$, respectively). It needs
145 to be noted that, within this age interval, additional trends might be hidden by the uncertainty
146 associated with the method used to estimate the ages of younger individuals.⁴² For whales ranging
147 between 9 and 29 years old, however, both the $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ value and the MeHg fraction decreased
148 systematically in the muscle tissue as a function of the individual's age: $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ is lowered by $\sim 0.9\text{‰}$ at
149 29 compared to at 9 years old (Spearman's correlation, $r = -1.000$, $p = 0.000$), while the MeHg fraction
150 in muscle decreased from 99 to 65% MeHg (Spearman's correlation, $r = -1.000$, $p = 0.000$). This was

151 found to be in good agreement with the compound-specificity of the Hg isotopic signatures. The
152 specific trend observed for muscle of adult whales from certain ages onwards suggests metabolic
153 changes in the whale body.^{48,49} The redistribution of Hg from highly contaminated organs, such as liver
154 (characterized by low $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values and a high iHg fraction), to muscle might be seen as a protective
155 mechanism against Hg toxicity.⁵⁰ In addition, we suggest that muscle loss at older age – the
156 replenishing of muscle is not at the same rate as the loss after a certain age – may be responsible for
157 this variation in the metabolism. The aging muscle is gradually storing more Hg under the form of iHg
158 species, while mobilization of the MeHg stored in this tissue occurs. An example of MeHg mobilization
159 as a function of muscle loss was reported on in literature for migrating birds.⁵¹ During migration, the
160 birds lost an important amount of muscle, inducing a mobilization of MeHg stored in this tissue. The
161 mobilized MeHg can be transported *via* the bloodstream to vital organs, such as brain, where it can
162 cause neurological damage that has hypothetically been identified as the origin of loss of orientation
163 while traveling long distances.^{52,53} Next to the redistribution of Hg from contaminated vital organs in
164 adult whales, an increase in the level of MeHg demethylation (assuming preferential demethylation of
165 the lighter Hg isotopes) into less toxic iHg species, *e.g.*, under the form of HgSe particles that remain
166 in the muscle tissue, together with the mobilization of MeHg, may explain both the reduction of the
167 MeHg fraction and the lighter bulk Hg isotopic composition of muscle tissues for the oldest whales.

168 *Liver*

169 In contrast to muscle, the MeHg fraction in liver is generally low, showing a clearly more pronounced
170 decrease for individuals ranging from 1 to 6 years old (see Figure 3B). At these low ages (≤ 6 years old),
171 both the $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ value and the MeHg fraction decrease following the same pattern (Spearman's
172 correlation, $r = 0.939$, $p = 0.000$), which is in agreement with the enrichment of lighter isotopes in the
173 iHg fraction. The different $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ trends are hypothesized to be related with both differences in diet
174 and in Hg metabolism between juvenile and adult whales. Honda *et al.* suggested a higher food intake
175 for younger Antarctic minke whales (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*) than for older animals.^{54,55}

176 Additionally, very low excretion rates by the fetus, specific requirements in newborns and differences
177 in tissues undergoing rapid development may explain the different Hg metabolic pathways of long-
178 finned pilot whales as a function of the individuals' age (these mechanisms will be discussed into detail
179 below).^{6,56-59}

180 To assess the influence of MeHg intake from the placenta (*in utero* exposure during gestation) and/or
181 from mother's milk during lactation on the MeHg fraction and Hg isotopic signature for juvenile whales,
182 the isotopic trend observed for the youngest whales was compared with the Hg isotopic signatures of
183 14 blood samples and 1 milk sample from a lactating whale (see Supplementary Table 5). In previous
184 studies of dolphins (*Stenella coeruleoalba*, *Sotalia guianensis* and *Tursiops truncatus*), high MeHg
185 exposure *via* the placenta was reported, whereas Hg concentrations in mother milk were found to be
186 higher than those in the prey fish of adult animals.^{60,61} Additionally, high MeHg concentrations have
187 been reported for breast milk from lactating women exposed to MeHg *via* the diet,⁶² and for rats and
188 mice (Holtzman rat and Balb/c CUM mice).^{63,64} In this work, relatively constant and high $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values
189 ($\sim 1\text{‰}$) were observed for all blood samples (blood can be related with *in utero* exposure), while the
190 milk sample was characterized by a $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ value that is significantly lower than that of the blood
191 sample and similar to that of muscle tissue ($0.12 \pm 0.03\text{‰}$) from the same whale. Compared to the
192 corresponding blood sample, the Hg isotopic composition of the milk sample was found to be shifted
193 towards the values observed for liver tissues of the youngest whales. Based on these results and on
194 previous studies on MeHg transfer across the placenta and on MeHg in mother's milk during lactation,
195 we suggest that during the first years of life, the isotopic composition of Hg in the liver is affected by a
196 strong contribution of MeHg originating from the mother, leading to anomalously higher $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values
197 in the liver of juvenile whales. MeHg from the placenta is mainly related with the mother's blood,
198 characterized by high $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ ($\sim 1\text{‰}$), while the introduction of MeHg from lactation already leads to
199 lower $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values ($\sim 0.10\text{‰}$). With the slow introduction of solid food in the diet, $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ tends to
200 even lower values. This gradual trend in diet and thus, in MeHg source, may explain the trend observed
201 for the $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ value and MeHg fraction in liver tissue of juvenile long-finned pilot whales. It needs to

202 be pointed out that the influence of mother's milk was based on a single lactating whale only.
203 Nevertheless, the results for that only milk sample available fits within the Hg isotopic data obtained
204 in this work for different tissues and biofluids of long-finned pilot whales and its interpretation was
205 found to be in good agreement with previous hypotheses reported on in literature (see above). Since
206 reliable toxicity data for marine mammals are scarce, the results obtained during this type of post-
207 mortem studies provide valuable information for a better understanding of the complex Hg
208 biochemistry in whales.

209 In addition to the differences in diet and Hg exposure pathways between juvenile and adult whales
210 indicated above, the influence of detoxification mechanisms developed in an attempt to mitigate the
211 toxic effects of Hg cannot be discarded as a potential explanation for the fast decrease in the MeHg
212 fraction, *i.e.*, in comparison with the increase in THg concentration, as a function of age. In previous
213 works, it has been reported that young marine mammals show higher percentages of MeHg than do
214 adult animals, suggesting that they do not reach a specific threshold.⁶⁵ Also, it has been hypothesized
215 that young marine mammals are unable to demethylate MeHg efficiently, since the corresponding
216 detoxification mechanism only develops at higher age.⁶⁶ Interestingly, a clear and rather abrupt change
217 in the $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ vs MeHg fraction trend was observed for liver as of an age of approximately 6 years old
218 (Figure 3B); it needs to be noted that the estimation of complete weaning is 6 years for short-finned
219 pilot whales, thus potentially indicating the development of more efficient detoxification mechanisms
220 to avoid Hg poisoning.⁶⁷ As of that age, the decrease in the liver MeHg fraction – from ~ 6 to 1% for
221 individuals between 5 – 6 and 35.5 years old – is accompanied by a progressive enrichment in the
222 heavier Hg isotopes (to ~1 ‰), an anomalous behavior that cannot be explained by the preferential
223 demethylation of lighter Hg isotopes. Masbou *et al.* have very recently reported the same $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ trend
224 as a function of the MeHg fraction in livers of beluga whales (*Delphinapterus leucas*).⁴¹ In that work,
225 the Hg isotopic trend was tentatively explained by factors such as lifetime changes in foraging behavior
226 or ecosystem MDF, as both products from *in vivo* hepatic MeHg breakdown are retained within the
227 whale organism (and within the liver) owing to the lack of other more efficient MeHg excretion

228 pathways, such as those observed in other marine mammals, *e.g.*, ringed seals (hair).^{68,69} Perrot *et al.*
229 also suggested that after MeHg demethylation, the product (iHg) and the residual MeHg can be
230 distributed to different organs and tissues by the bloodstream, where they are likely complexed by
231 specific ligands.¹¹ Unfortunately, none of the works cited above reports on the Hg isotopic composition
232 of muscle tissues as a function of the age. Based on our results, a continuous recirculation of both iHg
233 and MeHg between liver and muscle can most likely explain the trends in the $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values for liver
234 and muscle, as for the oldest whales, the $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values of both tissue types converge towards the same
235 value (see Figures 2 and 3).

236 In addition to these mechanisms, excretion processes, characterized by preferential removal of lighter
237 Hg isotopes, might also contribute to the trend observed in liver of long-finned pilot whales.^{45,70} In
238 previous works based on different species, including fish and humans, it was observed that only a
239 fraction of the iHg generated by MeHg demethylation processes accumulates in liver, while another
240 fraction is excreted from the liver *via* the urine or feces.^{44,71} In order to provide further insight into the
241 excretion mechanisms, kidney tissues were studied for their Hg isotopic composition. However, the
242 clear differences in tendency observed for $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ in liver between juvenile and adult whales were not
243 found for kidney (see Supplementary Figure 5).

244 Also, next to the commonly reported MeHg breakdown resulting in other iHg species, the formation
245 of inert HgSe particles aiming to counteract Hg intoxication has been demonstrated to play an
246 important role in MeHg detoxification, and their formation and associated isotope fractionation need
247 to be taken into account (see next section).

248

249 **Evidence for development of mercury detoxification pathways in long-finned pilot whales**

250 As it was found that an important fraction of the Hg accumulated in the liver is present under the form
251 of HgSe particles, the formation of these less toxic or even inert particles is assumed to be crucial in
252 Hg detoxification.^{17,18,66} Se has a protective effect against Hg toxicity owing to the Hg-Se antagonism.⁷²

253 Previous works reported a strong positive correlation between Hg and Se concentrations in muscle
254 tissues of five different species of toothed whales,⁷³ and in liver, kidney and muscle of long-finned pilot
255 whales.¹⁷ This correlation suggests that Se-mediated MeHg demethylation processes might take place
256 in the whale body. Therefore, the so-called Hg-Se antagonistic effect seems to be responsible for the
257 decrease of the MeHg fraction as a function of age, and for the increase in THg concentrations in liver,
258 kidney and muscle tissues as a result of the formation of less toxic HgSe particles.^{11,74}

259 According to the mechanisms proposed, the formation of crystalline HgSe is mediated by Hg–
260 metallothionein (Hg-MT) interaction and/or by Hg–Se binding in high-molecular-weight
261 substances.^{22,75} These mechanisms have been mainly observed in the liver of marine mammals,
262 stressing the key role of this organ in the biochemistry of Hg. In addition to liver, HgSe particles have
263 also been found in other tissues, such as brain, kidney, lung, muscle, pancreas, pituitary and
264 spleen.^{17,76,77} The formation process of HgSe particles in marine mammals is still poorly understood
265 and important knowledge gaps, including the Hg species acting as precursor(s), possible mechanisms
266 and the accompanying Hg isotope fractionation, exist. To obtain further insight, HgSe particles
267 extracted from liver and muscle tissues were analyzed for their Hg isotopic composition (the protocol
268 for extraction and confirmation of the identity of HgSe particles is reported elsewhere¹⁷). The results
269 are shown in Supplementary Table 6 and in Figure 4. $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values of HgSe particles from muscle were
270 found to be lower than that of THg in the corresponding muscle tissue (mostly MeHg), *i.e.*, the HgSe
271 particles are enriched in the lighter Hg isotopes. This observation is in agreement with the preferential
272 precipitation of lighter isotopes observed in the formation of metacinnabar ($\beta\text{-HgS}$) and montroydite
273 (HgO).⁷⁸ In contrast to muscle, $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values of HgSe particles from liver were always higher than that
274 of THg in the corresponding liver tissue. It needs to be stressed that this at first sight opposite trend
275 can be clarified by taking into account that in both tissue types – liver and muscle – the THg isotopic
276 composition is a combination (weighted average) of the Hg isotopic compositions of the different Hg
277 species (MeHg and iHg) present. In the case of liver, most of the Hg is in the form of iHg, while only a
278 small fraction of MeHg is present (the percentage of MeHg in liver is a function of the individual's age).

279 Perrot *et al.*¹¹ demonstrated that after MeHg breakdown in the liver, the product iHg is enriched in the
280 lighter Hg isotopes, while the remaining MeHg is enriched in the heavier ones. Therefore, to elucidate
281 the type and extent of fractionation induced by the formation of HgSe particles in the liver (mixture of
282 iHg and MeHg), the Hg species acting as precursor needs to be taking into account. HgSe particles can
283 theoretically form from either iHg compounds resulting from a previous *in vivo* demethylation, or
284 directly from MeHg as part of a detoxification mechanism.^{16,22} If we tentatively assume that the same
285 fractionation (direction) is accompanying the formation of HgSe particles in muscle and liver tissues of
286 long-finned pilot whales, then the HgSe particles must stem from MeHg demethylation. The process
287 of HgSe formation from MeHg would then in both tissues be accompanied by isotope fractionation in
288 favor of the lighter isotopes. However, it needs to be pointed out that Hg isotopic analysis of the
289 different Hg species (species-specific Hg isotopic analysis) would be required to experimentally verify
290 this hypothesis and accurately assess the extent of this fractionation. In the absence of species-specific
291 Hg isotopic compositions, the assumption of HgSe particles as a product of MeHg demethylation is
292 supported by (i) the formation of HgSe particles as of early ages, although to a lesser extent for juvenile
293 than for adult whales,¹⁷ (ii) the lack of mobility of HgSe particles *i.e.*, they stay at the “location” of their
294 formation,^{76,77} and (iii) the occurrence of HgSe particles in muscle tissue of juvenile whales (Hg for
295 ~100% present as MeHg). This explains the differences in $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ between the HgSe particles and the
296 corresponding isotopic composition of THg for both tissue types (based on the assumption of a heavier
297 Hg isotopic composition of the MeHg in the liver), although the influence of this process on the $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$
298 trends of liver and muscle tissues as a function of age is not self-evident. However, it needs to be noted
299 that the extent of the associated Hg isotope fractionation induced during HgSe formation (based on
300 the assumption that HgSe particles are a product of MeHg demethylation and on an estimation using
301 isotopic analysis of THg, instead of species-specific isotopic analysis) seems relatively low compared to
302 that accompanying the more “conventional” MeHg breakdown into other iHg species.

303 We suggest that with the increase in the THg concentration in liver and muscle tissues as a function of
304 age, the formation of other iHg species is increasingly replaced by the formation of HgSe particles. In

305 this case, the relatively low extent of Hg isotope fractionation associated with HgSe formation (see
306 Figure 4) most likely contributes to the trends observed for the $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ value in muscle and liver tissues
307 of adult whales.

308 Further investigation into the complex Hg biochemistry in marine mammals is still required in order to
309 shed more light onto this complex system. However, this work demonstrates that the information
310 attainable using Hg isotopic analysis may help to increase our understanding of the different Hg
311 metabolic processes occurring during the lifespan of long-finned pilot whales.

312 **Methods**

313 Samples were taken from 21 pilot whales (*Globicephala melas*) that died upon stranding at a beach
314 between Ansturther and Pittenween in Scotland, United Kingdom. Sampling was carried out under
315 the lead of the Scottish Stranding scheme. In agreement with the Convention on International Trade
316 in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), a European Protected Species license justified
317 the possession and analysis of cetacean samples. All samples (0.2 – 1.2 g wet weight) and certified
318 reference materials (CRMs – see Supplementary Table 8) used for validation purposes were acid-
319 digested in pre-cleaned closed microwave vessels using a Milestone (Italy) Ethos One High-
320 Performance Microwave Digestion System using a 3:1 mixture of 7 M HNO₃ and 9.8 M H₂O₂. The
321 microwave program is given in Supplementary Table 7. After the digestion, the samples were kept at
322 4 °C until THg quantification and Hg isotopic analysis.

323 For speciation (MeHg) analysis, the samples were solubilized in tetramethylammonium hydroxide,
324 buffered with acetate buffer, propylated with sodium tetrapropylborate (NaBPr₄), extracted into 2,2,4-
325 trimethylpentane and stored at -20 °C until analysis.^{9,79}

326 In addition, HgSe particles were isolated from the corresponding tissues following an enzymatic
327 digestion and their identity was corroborated (>90% HgSe), as reported on in a previous work from
328 Gajdosechova *et al.*¹⁷ The solubilization of these particles was done by adding a 3:1 mixture of 7 M
329 HNO₃ and 9.8 M H₂O₂.

330

331 **Elemental and speciation analysis**

332 Total Hg (THg) concentrations were determined using a ThermoScientific (Germany) Element XR single-
333 collector sector-field ICP-mass spectrometry instrument (SF-ICP-MS) working at low mass resolution,
334 as was previously described by Rua-Ibarz *et al.*^{80,81} For QA/QC of the entire analytical procedure, three
335 CRMs with similar matrix composition as those of the samples were analysed - BCR CRM 464 (tuna

336 fish), NRC-CNRC DORM-4 (fish muscle) and TORT-3 (lobster hepatopancreas) – and the Hg recoveries
337 obtained were between 93 – 107 %.

338 Hg speciation was performed at the University of Aberdeen using a HP-6890 GC-unit (Agilent
339 Technologies, Japan) coupled to an Agilent 7500 ICP-MS instrument (Agilent Technologies, Japan), as
340 previously described by Gajdosechova *et al.*⁹ The analytical method was validated using two CRMs –
341 NRC-CNRC DOLT-2 and DORM-2. The results obtained were in agreement with the certified values
342 (recoveries between 93 – 110 %)

343

344 **Mercury isotopic analysis**

345 Hg isotopic analysis was carried out using a ThermoScientific (Germany) Neptune multi-collector ICP-
346 MS (MC-ICP-MS) instrument equipped with nine Faraday cups. Hg was introduced as Hg(0) generated
347 *via* the reduction of Hg²⁺ with 3% SnCl₂·2H₂O in 1.2 M HCl in an HGX-200 cold vapor & hydride
348 generation unit (Teledyne Cetac Technologies, US). The Hg(0)-loaded carrier gas coming from the CVG
349 unit was admixed in a 'T' piece with a wet aerosol of Tl (used for internal mass discrimination correction
350 purposes) generated by using a 100 μL min⁻¹ concentric nebulizer mounted onto a dual (cyclonic and
351 Scott-type) spray chamber. A complete description of this set-up can be found in a previous manuscript
352 from the same authors.⁸⁰

353 For instrumental mass discrimination correction, a combination of internal correction using the
354 “Baxter approach” (with NIST SRM 997 Tl as admixed internal standard) and external correction in a
355 sample standard bracketing (SSB) approach (with NIST SRM 3133 Hg as external standard) was relied
356 on.^{80,82}

357 An in-house standard solution of Hg and the CRMs selected (see Supplementary Table 8) in this work
358 were measured in-between the samples (approximately every five samples) for QA/QC of the
359 measurements and of the entire analytical procedure (*i.e.*, MW acid digestion, storage, dilution and
360 subsequent MC-ICP-MS measurement).

361 The Hg concentration and acid content of all samples, standards and CRMs were matched within ± 10
362 % as to avoid inaccurate results. No blank subtraction was applied because the effect of the blank was
363 demonstrated to be negligible within the experimental precision.

364 The Hg isotopic composition is reported in delta ($\delta^{xxx}\text{Hg}$) and capital delta ($\Delta^{xxx}\text{Hg}$) notation – in per mil
365 units (‰) – for mass-dependent (MDF) and mass-independent (MIF) fractionation, respectively.⁸³

366

$$367 \quad \delta^{xxx}\text{Hg} (\text{‰}) = \left(\frac{({}^{xxx}\text{Hg}/{}^{198}\text{Hg})_{\text{sample}}}{({}^{xxx}\text{Hg}/{}^{198}\text{Hg})_{\text{NIST SRM 3133}}} - 1 \right) * 1000$$

368 where xxx = 199, 200, 201 or 202 and NIST SRM 3133 is the Hg isotopic reference material.

369

$$370 \quad \Delta^{199}\text{Hg} = \delta^{199}\text{Hg} - (\delta^{202}\text{Hg} * 0.2520)$$

$$371 \quad \Delta^{200}\text{Hg} = \delta^{200}\text{Hg} - (\delta^{202}\text{Hg} * 0.5024)$$

$$372 \quad \Delta^{201}\text{Hg} = \delta^{201}\text{Hg} - (\delta^{202}\text{Hg} * 0.7520)$$

373

374 Following the recommendations of Blum and Bergquist,⁸³ the analytical uncertainty or long-term
375 external reproducibility of the method has been reported as 2SD of the in-house standard, while for
376 the reference materials, the uncertainty was indicated as 2SE obtained upon replicate analysis (see
377 Supplementary Table 8). The results obtained for the samples analyzed in this work and shown in
378 Supplementary Tables 2-6 are also expressed as average \pm 2SE of the measured replicates. For most of
379 the cases, the 2SE values were found to be lower than the external reproducibility of the method, and
380 therefore, the 2SD values of the in-house standard have been reported in all Figures.

381

382

383

384 **Acknowledgements**

385 Eduardo Bolea-Fernandez acknowledges BOF-UGent for his postdoctoral grant. We acknowledge
386 Arnout Laureys for his support, Jonas Kunigkeit and Magali Perez for isolation of HgSe particles, and
387 Dr. Andrew Brownlow for given access to the Pilot Whale samples.

388

389 **Author contributions**

390 F.V., E.B.-F. and J.F. initiated this study; J.F. and E.M.K. collected the samples and conducted part of
391 the experiments; E.B. and A.R. carried through the majority of the experimental work (elemental assay
392 and high-precision Hg isotopic analysis) and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. All authors
393 contributed to discussion of the results and conclusions and to the writing process.

394

395 **Additional information**

396 **Supplementary information** accompanies this paper at <http://www.nature.com/srep>

397 **Competing interests:** The authors declare no competing financial and non-financial interests.

398

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602

603

604 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

605 **Figure 1.** THg concentration (black, in mg Kg^{-1} w.w.) and % MeHg (red) as a function of age for muscle
606 (A) and liver (B) tissues of long-finned pilot whales. The error bars correspond with the SD of three
607 digestion replicates.

608 **Figure 2.** Overview of the MDF-Hg isotopic signatures ($\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$) of different tissues of long-finned pilot
609 whales as a function of age. The uncertainty reported is the external reproducibility (2SD, $n = 147$) for
610 the in-house standard.

611 **Figure 3.** $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ (black – left y-axis) and MeHg fraction (% MeHg, red – right y-axis) obtained for muscle
612 (A) and liver (B) as a function of age. Uncertainty expressed as 2SD of the in-house standard.

613 **Figure 4.** $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values for liver and muscle tissues and for the corresponding isolated HgSe particles.
614 Uncertainty expressed as 2SD of the in-house standard.

616

618

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

High-precision isotopic analysis sheds new light on mercury metabolism in long-finned pilot whales (*Globicephala melas*)

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Supplementary Table 1. Information on the pod of whales analyzed in this work

Whale ID	Age (years)	Gender	Length (cm)
1	2.5	F	291
2	25.5	F	420
3	17	F**	389
4	25*	F**	420
5	20	F**	411
6	1*	F	192
7	1*	F	191
8	1*	F	194
9	6*	M	333
10	4	F	291
11	29	F**	445
12	3	F	315
13	9	F	360
14	2.5	M	296
15	35.5	F	462
16	4	M	318
17	2	M	287
18	25	F	440
19	15	M	444
20	28	F	435
21	16	M	538

*Age estimated based on body length

**Lactating mothers

Supplementary Table 2. THg (reported in mg Kg⁻¹ w.w.), % MeHg and Hg isotopic composition measured in liver tissue of long-finned pilot whales. The uncertainty is reported as 2SE for three sample replicates.

Whale ID	Age (years)	THg (mg Kg ⁻¹)	% MeHg	$\delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{200}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ (‰)
6	1	0.98 ± 0.10	32.1	0.89 ± 0.05	-0.32 ± 0.08	0.34 ± 0.05	-0.65 ± 0.12	1.05 ± 0.04	0.83 ± 0.06
7	1	1.33 ± 0.26	28.2	0.98 ± 0.06	-0.29 ± 0.02	0.46 ± 0.08	-0.57 ± 0.04	1.12 ± 0.06	0.89 ± 0.10
8	1	0.98 ± 0.15	28.3	0.89 ± 0.12	-0.10 ± 0.09	0.70 ± 0.07	-0.23 ± 0.15	0.94 ± 0.12	0.87 ± 0.05
1	2.5	5.9 ± 1.0	18.6	0.81 ± 0.08	-0.40 ± 0.06	0.17 ± 0.06	-0.97 ± 0.05	1.05 ± 0.09	0.89 ± 0.07
12	3	8.7 ± 1.1	14.9	0.79 ± 0.06	-0.43 ± 0.04	0.18 ± 0.03	-0.97 ± 0.07	1.04 ± 0.06	0.91 ± 0.08
10	4	27.4 ± 4.7	5.9	0.70 ± 0.05	-0.55 ± 0.04	-0.03 ± 0.05	-1.12 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.05	0.81 ± 0.05
13	9	57.7 ± 8.2	4.8	0.78 ± 0.02	-0.44 ± 0.03	0.16 ± 0.08	-0.91 ± 0.04	1.00 ± 0.03	0.84 ± 0.08
Females	3	147 ± 18	3.6	0.88 ± 0.08	-0.29 ± 0.04	0.31 ± 0.04	-0.65 ± 0.03	1.04 ± 0.08	0.80 ± 0.06
	5	148 ± 21	2.2	0.92 ± 0.02	-0.24 ± 0.01	0.44 ± 0.07	-0.57 ± 0.05	1.06 ± 0.03	0.87 ± 0.06
	18	243 ± 36	2.6	0.82 ± 0.06	-0.30 ± 0.03	0.34 ± 0.09	-0.65 ± 0.07	0.99 ± 0.06	0.84 ± 0.05
	4	208 ± 10	2.4	0.73 ± 0.05	-0.36 ± 0.02	0.19 ± 0.07	-0.81 ± 0.09	0.93 ± 0.07	0.80 ± 0.01
	2	234 ± 27	2.5	0.98 ± 0.03	-0.21 ± 0.03	0.49 ± 0.01	-0.58 ± 0.05	1.13 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.03
	20	472 ± 88	0.9	0.96 ± 0.05	-0.13 ± 0.07	0.55 ± 0.03	-0.35 ± 0.09	1.05 ± 0.03	0.81 ± 0.05
	11	415 ± 26	1.2	0.94 ± 0.04	-0.08 ± 0.04	0.66 ± 0.02	-0.29 ± 0.05	1.01 ± 0.04	0.87 ± 0.03
	15	608 ± 71	1.0	1.01 ± 0.03	-0.01 ± 0.05	0.78 ± 0.03	-0.15 ± 0.03	1.05 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.04
	17	2.61 ± 0.44	22.6	0.95 ± 0.02	-0.36 ± 0.03	0.39 ± 0.05	-0.74 ± 0.03	1.13 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.07
	14	6.14 ± 0.55	15.4	0.78 ± 0.08	-0.44 ± 0.10	0.10 ± 0.09	-0.95 ± 0.13	1.02 ± 0.05	0.82 ± 0.01
Males	16	8.6 ± 1.2	14.2	0.77 ± 0.05	-0.47 ± 0.03	0.10 ± 0.09	-0.98 ± 0.04	1.02 ± 0.04	0.84 ± 0.06
	9	43.9 ± 3.5	6.3	0.71 ± 0.05	-0.60 ± 0.03	-0.03 ± 0.11	-1.23 ± 0.09	1.02 ± 0.05	0.89 ± 0.09
	19	58.2 ± 11	4.0	0.80 ± 0.06	-0.45 ± 0.04	0.13 ± 0.05	-0.92 ± 0.07	1.03 ± 0.08	0.82 ± 0.03
	21	214 ± 28	1.6	0.83 ± 0.05	-0.33 ± 0.06	0.25 ± 0.08	-0.69 ± 0.05	1.00 ± 0.04	0.77 ± 0.04

Supplementary Table 3. THg (reported in mg Kg⁻¹ w.w.), % MeHg and Hg isotopic composition measured in kidney tissue of long-finned pilot whales. The uncertainty is reported as 2SE for three sample replicates.

Whale ID	Age (years)	THg (mg Kg ⁻¹)	% MeHg	$\delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{200}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ (‰)
6	1	0.60 ± 0.25	32.8	0.89 ± 0.08	-0.33 ± 0.09	0.32 ± 0.08	-0.76 ± 0.15	1.08 ± 0.05	0.89 ± 0.04
7	1	0.54 ± 0.08	41.9	0.94 ± 0.09	-0.33 ± 0.06	0.34 ± 0.13	-0.64 ± 0.13	1.11 ± 0.08	0.83 ± 0.03
8	1	0.42 ± 0.09	32.2	0.92 ± 0.09	-0.14 ± 0.04	0.51 ± 0.06	-0.33 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.09	0.76 ± 0.07
1	2.5	1.07 ± 0.10	46.5	1.00 ± 0.07	-0.09 ± 0.02	0.68 ± 0.12	-0.29 ± 0.05	1.07 ± 0.07	0.90 ± 0.11
12	3	1.31 ± 0.58	40.9	0.88 ± 0.05	-0.17 ± 0.05	0.52 ± 0.11	-0.39 ± 0.06	0.98 ± 0.04	0.81 ± 0.06
10	4	1.8 ± 1.0	33.7	0.89 ± 0.05	-0.24 ± 0.04	0.50 ± 0.06	-0.47 ± 0.04	1.01 ± 0.04	0.86 ± 0.06
13	9	6.3 ± 1.3	13.2	0.77 ± 0.07	-0.54 ± 0.04	0.02 ± 0.08	-1.10 ± 0.06	1.05 ± 0.08	0.85 ± 0.04
Females	3	5.15 ± 0.74	28.7	0.75 ± 0.08	-0.32 ± 0.02	0.31 ± 0.04	-0.62 ± 0.06	0.91 ± 0.09	0.78 ± 0.01
	5	9.8 ± 3.8	10.4	0.89 ± 0.04	-0.24 ± 0.05	0.45 ± 0.03	-0.52 ± 0.08	1.02 ± 0.02	0.84 ± 0.04
	18	15.0 ± 5.5	10.5	0.83 ± 0.05	-0.41 ± 0.07	0.33 ± 0.11	-0.82 ± 0.11	1.03 ± 0.05	0.95 ± 0.04
	4	4.31 ± 1.2	11.7	0.89 ± 0.06	-0.32 ± 0.04	0.25 ± 0.13	-0.63 ± 0.05	1.05 ± 0.07	0.73 ± 0.10
	2	10.6 ± 0.9	12.8	0.90 ± -0.02	-0.32 ± 0.03	0.29 ± 0.05	-0.76 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.03	0.86 ± 0.03
	20	20.7 ± 1.3	4.7	0.86 ± 0.03	-0.33 ± 0.12	0.38 ± 0.09	-0.67 ± 0.12	1.03 ± 0.01	0.88 ± 0.08
	11	21.8 ± 2.8	7.6	0.84 ± 0.03	-0.33 ± 0.06	0.35 ± 0.12	-0.72 ± 0.05	1.02 ± 0.04	0.88 ± 0.11
	15	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
	17	1.22 ± 0.21	24.6	0.76 ± 0.05	-0.50 ± 0.08	0.11 ± 0.14	-1.02 ± 0.15	1.02 ± 0.05	0.87 ± 0.06
	14	1.93 ± 0.44	26.1	0.85 ± 0.06	-0.31 ± 0.08	0.36 ± 0.08	-0.71 ± 0.08	1.03 ± 0.04	0.89 ± 0.03
Males	16	2.99 ± 0.49	24.2	0.87 ± 0.06	-0.33 ± 0.01	0.34 ± 0.05	-0.73 ± 0.08	1.06 ± 0.08	0.89 ± 0.02
	9	2.80 ± 0.10	34.2	0.98 ± 0.02	-0.25 ± 0.06	0.46 ± 0.04	-0.55 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.02	0.87 ± 0.02
	19	6.03 ± 0.62	26.2	0.89 ± 0.02	-0.35 ± 0.02	0.34 ± 0.05	-0.73 ± 0.06	1.07 ± 0.01	0.89 ± 0.04
	21	7.0 ± 1.4	11.1	0.85 ± 0.04	-0.41 ± 0.01	0.29 ± 0.07	-0.78 ± 0.07	1.05 ± 0.03	0.88 ± 0.05

N.A. = not available

Supplementary Table 4. THg (reported in mg Kg⁻¹ w.w.), % MeHg and Hg isotopic composition measured in muscle tissue of long-finned pilot whales. The uncertainty is reported as 2SE for three sample replicates.

Whale ID	Age (years)	THg (mg Kg ⁻¹)	% MeHg	δ ¹⁹⁹ Hg (‰)	δ ²⁰⁰ Hg (‰)	δ ²⁰¹ Hg (‰)	δ ²⁰² Hg (‰)	Δ ¹⁹⁹ Hg (‰)	Δ ²⁰¹ Hg (‰)	
	6	1	0.51 ± 0.15	89.7	1.38 ± 0.12	0.57 ± 0.11	1.70 ± 0.09	1.03 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.13	0.93 ± 0.06
	7	1	0.61 ± 0.06	100.0	1.39 ± 0.06	0.59 ± 0.04	1.71 ± 0.05	1.05 ± 0.11	1.13 ± 0.09	0.92 ± 0.06
	8	1	0.50 ± 0.09	78.7	1.23 ± 0.11	0.54 ± 0.01	1.58 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.04	0.99 ± 0.12	0.84 ± 0.05
	1	2.5	0.95 ± 0.05	100.0	1.28 ± 0.05	0.48 ± 0.04	1.60 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.03	1.04 ± 0.06	0.86 ± 0.04
	12	3	1.51 ± 0.25	N.A.	1.37 ± 0.06	0.68 ± 0.05	1.84 ± 0.07	1.31 ± 0.09	1.04 ± 0.06	0.85 ± 0.03
	10	4	1.51 ± 0.21	86.1	1.35 ± 0.03	0.62 ± 0.04	1.72 ± 0.09	1.13 ± 0.09	1.07 ± 0.04	0.87 ± 0.03
	13	9	3.15 ± 0.63	99.0	1.34 ± 0.06	0.53 ± 0.07	1.68 ± 0.08	1.07 ± 0.03	1.07 ± 0.06	0.87 ± 0.06
Females	3	17	4.2 ± 0.65	89.6	1.32 ± 0.07	0.55 ± 0.01	1.62 ± 0.05	0.98 ± 0.07	1.08 ± 0.09	0.88 ± 0.03
	5	20	4.2 ± 0.65	87.2	1.33 ± 0.02	0.47 ± 0.01	1.53 ± 0.04	0.80 ± 0.04	1.13 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.04
	18	25	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
	4	25	3.84 ± 0.38	75.4	1.17 ± 0.06	0.34 ± 0.09	1.43 ± 0.06	0.71 ± 0.04	0.99 ± 0.06	0.89 ± 0.08
	2	25.5	3.82 ± 0.9	67.5	1.15 ± 0.09	0.29 ± 0.03	1.29 ± 0.01	0.55 ± 0.04	1.01 ± 0.10	0.87 ± 0.03
	20	28	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
	11	29	4.72 ± 0.35	65.3	1.19 ± 0.03	0.16 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.11	0.20 ± 0.10	1.14 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.04
	15	35.5	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
	17	2	1.04 ± 0.15	87.2	1.36 ± 0.07	0.58 ± 0.02	1.67 ± 0.04	1.05 ± 0.05	1.10 ± 0.08	0.88 ± 0.05
	14	2.5	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
Males	16	4	1.26 ± 0.15	88.2	1.37 ± 0.05	0.57 ± 0.08	1.72 ± 0.13	1.01 ± 0.06	1.12 ± 0.04	0.96 ± 0.14
	9	6	1.69 ± 0.34	93.7	1.37 ± 0.03	0.50 ± 0.07	1.72 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.08	1.13 ± 0.01	1.01 ± 0.07
	19	15	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
	21	16	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.

N.A. = not available

Supplementary Table 5. Hg isotopic composition measured in blood and milk of long-finned pilot whales. The uncertainty is reported as 2SE for three sample replicates.

	Whale ID	Age (years)	$\delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{200}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ (‰)
Blood Females	6	1	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
	7	1	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
	8	1	1.27 ± 0.05	0.61 ± 0.05	1.64 ± 0.11	0.98 ± 0.17	1.02 ± 0.06	0.90 ± 0.01
	1	2.5	1.35 ± 0.08	0.52 ± 0.03	1.63 ± 0.14	1.01 ± 0.05	1.10 ± 0.08	0.88 ± 0.11
	12	3	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
	10	4	1.36 ± 0.11	0.57 ± 0.02	1.75 ± 0.10	1.15 ± 0.04	1.07 ± 0.10	0.88 ± 0.07
	13	9	1.35 ± 0.12	0.69 ± 0.12	1.82 ± 0.06	1.18 ± 0.07	1.05 ± 0.13	0.93 ± 0.08
	3	17	1.43 ± 0.15	0.71 ± 0.13	1.80 ± 0.12	1.27 ± 0.15	1.11 ± 0.14	0.84 ± 0.04
	5	20	1.44 ± 0.05	0.61 ± 0.10	1.78 ± 0.06	1.10 ± 0.11	1.16 ± 0.06	0.95 ± 0.08
	18	25	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
	4	25	1.37 ± 0.06	0.59 ± 0.05	1.70 ± 0.05	1.04 ± 0.02	1.11 ± 0.06	0.92 ± 0.07
	2	25.5	1.31 ± 0.03	0.57 ± 0.06	1.68 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.03	1.06 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.01
	20	28	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
	11	29	1.42 ± 0.06	0.53 ± 0.06	1.69 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.11	1.17 ± 0.06	0.96 ± 0.08
	15	35.5	1.36 ± 0.05	0.47 ± 0.02	1.67 ± 0.09	0.90 ± 0.06	1.14 ± 0.05	0.99 ± 0.06
Blood Males	17	2	1.39 ± 0.05	0.61 ± 0.09	1.68 ± 0.10	1.03 ± 0.09	1.13 ± 0.04	0.91 ± 0.05
	14	2.5	1.41 ± 0.08	0.67 ± 0.06	1.85 ± 0.11	1.23 ± 0.08	1.10 ± 0.06	0.93 ± 0.06
	16	4	1.38 ± 0.05	0.59 ± 0.09	1.70 ± 0.06	1.07 ± 0.08	1.12 ± 0.04	0.96 ± 0.05
	9	6	1.35 ± 0.06	0.56 ± 0.08	1.65 ± 0.08	0.96 ± 0.15	1.11 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.04
	19	15	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
	21	16	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
Milk	11	29	1.18 ± 0.03	0.14 ± 0.05	1.06 ± 0.04	0.12 ± 0.04	1.15 ± 0.04	0.97 ± 0.04

N.A. = not available

Supplementary Table 6. Hg isotopic composition measured in the isolated HgSe nanoparticles from different tissues. The uncertainty is reported as 2SE for three sample replicates.

	Whale ID	Age (years)	$\delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{200}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ (‰)
Liver	14	2.5	0.68 ± 0.09	-0.38 ± 0.04	0.07 ± 0.03	-0.85 ± 0.06	0.89 ± 0.09	0.70 ± 0.02
	13	9	0.75 ± 0.09	-0.32 ± 0.06	0.20 ± 0.08	-0.74 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.08	0.76 ± 0.06
	3	17	0.77 ± 0.11	-0.18 ± 0.08	0.38 ± 0.10	-0.43 ± 0.13	0.88 ± 0.10	0.71 ± 0.06
	2	25.5	0.87 ± 0.07	-0.05 ± 0.05	0.71 ± 0.03	-0.14 ± 0.10	0.91 ± 0.08	0.81 ± 0.09
	11	29	0.84 ± 0.07	-0.01 ± 0.07	0.70 ± 0.04	-0.09 ± 0.07	0.86 ± 0.07	0.76 ± 0.08
Muscle	2	25.5	1.03 ± 0.03	0.11 ± 0.05	0.91 ± 0.07	0.18 ± 0.11	0.99 ± 0.03	0.78 ± 0.07
	11	29	0.94 ± 0.13	0.00 ± 0.08	0.76 ± 0.04	-0.01 ± 0.18	0.95 ± 0.17	0.77 ± 0.10

Supplementary Table 7. Microwave program used for microwave-assisted acid digestion in a Milestone Ethos One High-Performance Microwave Digestion System.

Step	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)
1	Room temperature to 70	5
2	70 to 90	7
3	90	5
4	90 to 120	7
5	120	5
6	120 to 150	7
7	150	5

Supplementary Table 8. Recoveries and mercury isotope ratio data for reference materials used for QA/QC. The uncertainty of the in-house standard is reported as 2SD because it is considered the external reproducibility of the method. For the other materials, the uncertainty is reported as 2SE for the different replicate measurements.¹

		n	Recovery THg (%)	Recovery MeHg (%)	
BCR CRM 464		3	101 ± 6	---	
NRC-CNRC DORM - 4		3	98 ± 5	---	
NRC-CNRC TORT - 3		3	98 ± 5	---	
NRC-CNRC DOLT - 2		3	---	103 ± 6	
NRC-CNRC DORM - 2		3	---	102 ± 8	
		n	$\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ (‰)
In-house standard		147	-0.59 ± 0.12	0.00 ± 0.12	0.00 ± 0.12
BCR CRM 464	This work	14	0.44 ± 0.07	2.09 ± 0.05	1.72 ± 0.03
	<i>Epov et al.</i> ²	7	0.59 ± 0.08	2.18 ± 0.03	1.79 ± 0.03
NRC-CNRC DORM - 4		4	0.32 ± 0.06	1.65 ± 0.12	1.26 ± 0.10
NRC-CNRC TORT - 3		3	-0.18 ± 0.05	0.54 ± 0.01	0.51 ± 0.10

Supplementary Figure 1. Three-isotope plots: $\delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (A), $\delta^{200}\text{Hg}$ (B) and $\delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ (C) vs $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ for all the samples analyzed in this work. The error bars are the SD of the average of all samples for each of the different tissues and biofluids.

Supplementary Figure 2. $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ as a function of % MeHg for liver (black squares) and muscle (blue triangles) tissues. Generally, $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values increase as a function of the MeHg fraction, except for livers with the lowest % MeHg. Uncertainty expressed as 2SD of the in-house standard.

Supplementary Figure 3. $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ vs $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values obtained for all tissue samples and biological fluids analyzed in this work. The error bars are the SD of the average of all samples for each of the different tissues and biofluids.

Supplementary Figure 4. $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ vs $\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ values obtained for all the samples analyzed in this work. The line represents the average $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}/\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ ratio (1.21). The uncertainty is the external reproducibility of the in-house standard.

Supplementary Figure 5. $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ (black – left y-axis) and MeHg fraction (% MeHg, red – right y-axis) obtained for kidney as a function of age. The uncertainty is the external reproducibility of the in-house standard.

Supplementary References

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